

Community Mapping of the TIDAL ArtS Residency Locations

São Miguel Island, Azores, Portugal

Venice Lagoon, Italy

Turku Archipelago, Finland

Danube River, Ráckeve, Hungary

TIDAL
ArtS

Transforming and Inspiring
Aquatic Landscapes Through
Art and Sciences

Funded by the European Union
under the Grant Agreement
Grant agreement ID 101157796.
Views and opinions expressed
are however those of the
author(s) only and do not
necessarily reflect those of the
European Union. Neither the
European Union nor the
granting authority can be held
responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

Azores - Portugal

Table 1. List of communities mapped in the region of Azores Archipelago.

Title	Description
Local NGOs, Charities & Foundations environment and art related	
432Hz Associação Cultural para as Artes e as Ciências	"432Hz - Cultural Association for the Arts and Sciences aims to promote art and science as a means of expression, reflection and enrichment of literacy in society. In particular, the association aims to encourage artistic creation, promoting the interdisciplinarity between art and science in the community offering educational opportunities through workshops, workshops, exhibitions and presentations". Source: https://project432hz.webnode.pt/
Expolab - Centro Ciência Viva	"Located in the City of Lagoa, it is one of the most important spaces for scientific dissemination in the archipelago. A place where visitors will find answers to several of the phenomena that surround us. Workshops, lectures, exhibitions, and workshops for all ages make a visit to this space essential for all those who visit the Azores". Source: https://www.cienciaviva.pt/en/ciencia-viva-centres-network/index.php?id_centro=25
Habitat Açores	"Habitat Açores was born out of a collective concern for the evolution of quality of life in the Azores". Source: https://habitatacores.wixsite.com/habitat-a-ores/sobre
The Ecological Association Friends of the Azores	"The Ecological Association Friends of the Azores is an association whose purpose is to defend and value the environment, as well as to promote the conservation of nature, privileging non-violent methods of work and intervention, through cultural, pedagogical, scientific, sporting, recreational, social or other related activities". Source: https://www.amigosdosazores.pt/
The Observatório do Mar dos Açores	"The Azores Sea Observatory (OMA) is a non-profit Technical, Scientific and Cultural Association". Source: https://www.oma.pt/oma.php
Azores Fisheries Federation	"The Azores Fisheries Federation (FPA) was founded in 2005 and was created by the will of the associative movement of the fishing sector in the Azores". Source: https://federacaopesacasazores.pt/sobre-nos/ e.g. Pico Artisanal Fisheries Association (APAP, No website — contact via institutional channels).
Porto de Abrigo Cooperative (São Miguel)	"Portos dos Açores is the Port Authority of Azores and its history goes back to 1810 when the first portuguese free port born in Ponta Delgada, island of São Miguel. In September of 2011, the three old extinguish port authorities of Azores (APSM, APTG and APTO) merged into one company Portos dos Açores, S.A.". Source: https://www.linkedin.com/company/portos-dos-a-ores-s-a/
The Blue Azores Program	"The Blue Azores Program was born in 2019 from a partnership between the Regional Government of the Azores, the Oceano Azul Foundation and the Waitt Institute, which came together around a common vision - to protect, promote and value the marine natural capital of the Azores - which supports an ambition to ensure a healthy ocean as the basis of a prosperous and sustainable blue economy". Source: https://www.blueazores.org/
NATURALIST (Faial)	"Founded by two University researchers who believe 'Sustainable tourism must include environmental data collection'". Source: https://www.naturalist.pt/
Terra Azul (São Miguel)	"Whale Watching and Wildlife Eco Expeditions – in the heart of the Atlantic Ocean!". Source: https://www.azoreswhalewatch.com/
Whale Museum (Museu dos Baleeiros) (Pico)	"The Whaling Industry Museum, former Fábrica da Baleia Armações Baleeiras Reunidas, Lda., in São Roque do Pico, is the first public industrial museum in the Azores". Source: http://www.museu-pico.azores.gov.pt/museu/museu-da-industria-tidalarts.eu

	baleeira/
Terra Nostra Botanical Garden (São Miguel)	<p>“Inserted in the Furnas Protected Landscape Area and situated in the parish centre, Terra Nostra Park, with 12.5 hectares, it is one of the most attractive places of Furnas. The entrance to the park is located in Largo Marquês da Praia e Monforte. It’s a botanical park of the 18th/19th centuries, characterized by its geothermal pool, landscape and vegetation richness and variety, being a true botanical museum”.</p> <p>Source: https://parquesnaturais.azores.gov.pt/en/parques/9/poi/115</p>
Jardim António Borges (São Miguel)	<p>“It dates from the century. XIX and was created by António Borges, an Azorean businessman and politician. Today it is municipal heritage and the green lung of the city center. It portrays the romantic and picturesque spirit of the nineteenth century and is used for the most diverse activities”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.visitpontadelgada.pt/pages/773/?geo_article_id=2652</p>
Botanical Garden of Faial	<p>“Open to the public since 1986, the Faial Botanical Garden consists of the altitude pole, in Pedro Miguel, and the central pole, in the parish of Flamengos, where the Azores Seed Bank is located. Its mission is related to the conservation and study of the natural flora of the Azores, scientific dissemination and environmental education”.</p> <p>Source: https://parquesnaturais.azores.gov.pt/pt/parques/3/centro/13</p>
Live Fish Station - Porto Pim Aquarium	<p>“The Live Fish Station – Porto Pim Aquarium is housed in a building full of history about the cod drought and was the first whale oil extraction factory. It includes a central tank and two sets of tanks with the most common coastal species of the Azores, an exhibition on the Azores Marine Park and a film on the deep sea of the continental shelf adjacent to the Archipelago. The promotion of knowledge about the biodiversity of the Azores sea, along with environmental awareness and recovery of sensitive marine animals, are the main missions that the Regional Secretariat for the Environment and Climate Action carries out in this unit” . Source: https://parquesnaturais.azores.gov.pt/pt/parques/3/centro/14 (temporary closed)</p>
Jardim José do Canto (São Miguel)	<p>“The José do Canto Botanical Garden is a public interest site (Resolution of the Azorean Government, nº 144/95, 10th August 1995), registered in the Botanic Gardens Conservation Secretariat, a branch of UNESCO, and it is featured in the World Guide of Botanic Gardens, published by the same organization”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.josedocanto.com/sobre-about</p>
Futurismo Azores Adventures (São Miguel, Faial, Pico)	<p>“Whale watching Azores”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.futurismo.pt/</p>
More marine Tourism groups	<p>List of Marine related tourism organisations:</p> <p>https://www.azores.gov.pt/NR/rdonlyres/4A9CBB38-360B-4866-B5C3-44F30CDE2085/1126217/aPASSEIOSMARTIMOTURSTICOS.pdf</p>
RARA – Rural Art and Architecture Residency (São Miguel)	<p>“RARA - Residência de Artesanato do Região dos Açores is a continuous production project of Anda&Fala - Cultural Association, started in 2014 in the context of its Walk&Talk - Festival de Artes It comprises two complementary aspects: annual artistic residencies and marketing of the products resulting from that moment under a private label”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.rara-azores.com/sobre</p>
Burra de Milho – Theatre and Nature (São Miguel)	<p>“The Burra de Milho Cultural Association aims to promote and dynamize the cultural and social world through the arts and creativity”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.facebook.com/Burra.de.milho/ https://burrademilho.blogspot.com/</p>
MiratecArts (Pico)	<p>“The MiratecArts Association aims to enhance the individual, the team and organizational productivity in the world of the arts. Produce, promote and present artists, shows and events covering the various artistic disciplines; to build</p>

	<p>educational cultural events and creative tourism for different generations; respect our nature as a canvas of art and place art in nature. Founded by a team led by Terry Costa, in 2012 in the Azores, the cultural entity is headquartered in Mirateca-Candelária, in the municipality of Madalena, Pico Island, in the Azores archipelago, Portugal”.</p> <p>Source: https://miratecart.com/projetos</p>
Quercus Açores (São Miguel)	<p>“Quercus is a Portuguese Non-Governmental Environmental Organization (NGO) of public utility, founded on October 31, 1985”. Source: https://quercus.pt/apresentacao/</p>
ACORES BIO – Azorean Biodiversity Association (São Miguel)	<p>“The Forum of Biological Agriculture - Açores Bio 23 - aims to present and promote the producers”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.facebook.com/Forumbioazores/ / https://forumbio.agricultura.azores.gov.pt/bio-regioes/</p>
Demersal Species Producers Association (APEDA) (Faial)	<p>“Association for the defense/help of fishing boat owners”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.facebook.com/apeda.azores/</p>
Cooperativa de Economia Solidária dos Pescadores de Ribeira Quente, C.R.L. (São Miguel)	<p>“The entity Cooperativa de Economia Solidária Pescadores de Ribeira Quente, C.R.L. has its headquarters located in the parish of Ribeira Quente, municipality of Povoação, district of Ilha de São Miguel”.</p> <p>Source: https://codigopostal.ciberforma.pt/dir/512050457/cooperativa-de-economia-solidaria-pescadores-de-ri/#google_vignette</p>
APASA – Azores Tuna and Similar Producers Association	<p>“Associação de Produtores de Atum e Similares dos Açores”.</p> <p>Source : https://apasa.pt/</p>
ARPLA – Regional Association for Recreational Fishing of the Azores	<p>“The Azores Recreational Fishing Association aims to unite all recreational and leisure fishermen in the Azores Archipelago under the same goal. Promoting sustainability is a central pillar of this association”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.facebook.com/pesca.ludica.acores/?locale=pt_PT</p>
ACPA	<p>“We help fish traders in the Azores to develop their activities, providing all the support they need and representing them in various forums”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.facebook.com/ACPAAcores/?locale=pt_PT</p>
OVGA – Azores Volcanological and Geothermal Observatory (São Miguel)	<p>“Dissemination centre for volcanological and geoenvironmental sciences, which among others, deals with issues related to the geodynamics of the Atlantic”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.visitazores.com/en/explore/volcanological-and-geothermal-observatory</p>
Furnas Environmental Interpretation Center (São Miguel)	<p>“The Furnas Environmental Interpretation Centre (CIAF) was created with the aim of disseminating the history and evolution of the Furnas Volcano, with an approach to biodiversity, geodiversity and natural and cultural heritage, the formation of the Azores and especially the island of São Miguel, and also the Management Plan of the Furnas Lagoon Hydrographic Basin and respective preventive measures implemented in the protection and recovery of ecosystems in the Protected Landscape Area of the Furnas”.</p> <p>Source: https://parquesnaturais.azores.gov.pt/pt/parques/9/centro/22</p>
Capelinhos Volcano Interpretation Center (Faial)	<p>“The Capelinhos Volcano Interpretation Centre has an informative, educational and scientific mission, and the building was constructed underground, so it would not interfere with the pre-existing landscape. It has a set of exhibitions about the Capelinhos Volcano’s eruption, the formation of the Archipelago, the most emblematic volcanos in the world and the history of the Azorean lighthouses. Besides the exhibitions, it also has an auditorium and a temporary exhibition of rock and mineral samples. It is possible to go up the Lighthouse and enjoy this recent volcanic landscape that originated from the eruption of 1957/58. This Centre was appointed by the European Museum Forum for the European Museum of the Year Award in 2012. Today, it’s all about sharing knowledge at the Ciência Viva Centres”.</p> <p>Source: https://parquesnaturais.azores.gov.pt/en/parques/3/centro/12</p>

NEA, "Group of Azorean Studies"	"In 1993, an ambitious project called Cultural Mapping of Azorean-based Culture was launched in Santa Catarina by the Núcleo de Estudos Açorianos (NEA, "Group of Azorean Studies"). This group, based at the Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC), is currently one of the most active organizations in the Azoreanist movement of Santa Catarina and works to discover the Azorean roots of the state, which date back to 1748 when 6,000 individuals from the Azores settled in the coastal areas of Santa Catarina". Source: https://journals.openedition.org/etnografica/2955
<i>Beyond Azores Archipelago</i>	
Madeira Whale Museum	"The Madeira Whale Museum is located in the village of Caniçal and is a testimony to the history of whaling in Madeira and the activities associated with it. The Madeira Whale Museum has been developing over the past few years, studies of cetaceans in the Madeira archipelago". Source: https://www.museudabaleia.org/en/the-museum/about-the-museum.html
ARTE.M Cultural and Artistic Association on Madeira Island	"We are dedicated to the promotion of culture & cultural education, artistic expression and raising awareness of the richness of Madeira history and undiscovered arts". Source: https://www.artmadeira.org/
MARE-Madeira	"The Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre (MARE) is a multi-regional marine research and development centre with seven research units across Portugal mainland and Madeira Island. Co-hosted by ARDITI and the University of Madeira, MARE-Madeira is the largest non-profit marine research institute in Madeira". Source: https://mare-madeira.pt/pt/
Local institutions and municipalities	
Instituto de Investigação em Ciências do Mar - Okeanos, Universidade dos Açores	"The Institute of Marine Sciences – OKEANOS, located in the city of Horta, Faia Island, is a recent research unit which heir more than 40 years of both applied and fundamental marine research conducted in the Azores by the Department of Oceanography and Fisheries (DOP) of the University of the Azores". Source: https://www.okeanos.uac.pt/about
The Atlantic International Research Centre	"The Atlantic International Research Centre is an international collaborative framework to address global challenges and local priorities in the Atlantic Ocean (...). On March 2025, sixteen states (or regions) cooperate through AIR Centre initiatives: Portugal, Azores, Spain, Nigeria, United Kingdom, Cabo Verde, Bahia (Brazil), South Africa, Morocco, Angola, Colombia, France, Guatemala, Peru, São Tomé e Príncipe and Madeira". Source: https://www.aircentre.org/about-us/
IMAR – Marine & Environmental Research Centre	"IMAR is a private non-profit association dedicated to the management of fundamental and applied research in its scientific field of activity at Portuguese level. Mission - To contribute to the national scientific and technological development in this scientific field, by supporting the networking of its members" Source: https://imar.org.pt/en/about-us/
FRCT – Regional Fund for Science and Technology (São Miguel)	"The Regional Science and Technology Fund (FRCT) is a public body supervised by the Vice-Presidency of the Regional Government of the Azores, with legal personality and endowed with administrative and financial autonomy". Source: https://frct.azores.gov.pt/en/homepage-english/
The Municipality of Ponta Delgada	Municipality in São Miguel Island, e.g. workshops on MPA. Source: https://www.cm-pontadelgada.pt/p/contactos
Municipality of Lagoa	Municipality in São Miguel Island, e.g. workshops on MPA. Source: https://www.lagoa-cores.pt/
Municipality of Ribeira Grande	Municipality in São Miguel Island, e.g. workshops on MPA. Source: www.cm-ribeiragrande.pt

Regional Directorate of Culture	Regional Directorate of Culture. Source: https://www.culturacores.azores.gov.pt/ajuda/Contactos.aspx
Projects and initiatives	
Habitat Azores (São Miguel)	“The HABILITAT program aims to strengthen the sense of belonging and appreciation for the place where people live, through the appreciation of history, experiences and traditions, as well as the preservation of the natural heritage”. Source: https://azoresburningsummer.com/habitat
Marine Waste Portugal / Oceanlit Azores	“Oceanlit Project. Management of coastal protected natural areas in island archipelagos affected by marine litter”. Source: https://www.oceanlitproject.com/
Youth4Ocean	“Our common goal is to shape our future with a healthy ocean that sustains us all”. Source: https://maritime-forum.ec.europa.eu/theme/ocean-literacy-and-blue-skills/ocean-literacy/youth4ocean-forum_en
AZORES2020	“The Azores 2020 OP is a programme co-funded by the Community Structural Funds ERDF and ESF, for the 2014-2020 programming period, with implementation in the Autonomous Region of the Azores”. Source: https://poacores2020.azores.gov.pt/programa-acores-2020/
Blue Azores Programme	“The Blue Azores Program brings together a team of specialists from various fields, all united by a passion for the Azorean Sea. Each team member contributes their unique skills and experiences to the program's success”. Source: https://www.blueazores.org/team
Futurismo – "Guardians of the Azores" project	“Embark on a citizen science adventure designed for families and the future. Cultivate critical thinking, promote environmental ties by keeping the coasts of our islands clean, and nurture civic pride”. Source: https://www.futurismo.pt/pt/guardioes-dos-acores/
Oceanic Café	FISHPICS® ILLUSTRATIONS, Source: https://www.azores-oceanic.com/fishpics-illustration
Azores Underwater Cultural Heritage	“The Azores Regional Directory of Cultural Affairs is a bureau of the Azores Regional Government dedicated to overseeing all affairs related to heritage issues, as well as artistic development of the Portuguese archipelago. Since the year 2000, all issues related to archaeological heritage have been autonomously managed by this regional governmental department and with was since then that five underwater archaeological parks have been created, as well as several protected areas, and the Underwater Archaeological Route, made up of the thirty visitable sites that have been awarded the joint European Heritage Label. Located in the city of Angra do Heroísmo, on Terceira Island, on the Azores, the Regional Directory of Cultural Affairs continues to manage these and many other issues, with the main mission of protecting, promoting and potentialize the Region's shared cultural heritage that binds the multicultural identity of the Atlantic Ocean”. Source: https://ehl-bureau.eu/en/project/azores-underwater-cultural-heritage/

Turku Archipelago, Finland

Table 2. List of communities mapped in the region of Turku Archipelago, Finland.

Title	Description
Local NGOs, Charities & Foundations environment and art related	
Pidä saaristo siistinä: Keep the Archipelago Tidy Association	<p>“The state of the Baltic Sea is a common concern, but the Keep the Archipelago Tidy Association also wants to draw attention to and safeguard the well-being of Finnish inland waterways. Join us and help take care of the Baltic Sea and our thousands of lakes”.</p> <p>Source: https://keepthearchipelagotidy.fi/</p>
Airisto Investment Fish Area	<p>“According to the Fisheries Act 379/2015, fishing areas are public-law associations whose purpose is to develop fisheries in their region and to promote co-operation between their members to organise the sustainable use and management of fishery resources”.</p> <p>Source: https://airistovelkua.fi/</p>
The Archipelago Unesco Biosphere Reserve	<p>“The Archipelago Sea biosphere reserve was established in 1994 and consists of the Archipelago Sea National Park and the parts of the archipelago that belong to the town of Pargas and the municipality of Kimitoön. This means the islands of Houtskär, Korpo, Nagu and Iniö as a whole, and parts of Pargas, Dragsfjärd, Västanfjärd and Kimito”.</p> <p>Source: https://biosfar.fi/en/the-biosphere-reserve/our-biosphere-reserve-2/</p>
The Regional Council of the South Coast	<p>“The Regional Council of the South Coast is tasked with supporting the work of high-quality services in Swedish in education and culture in its member municipalities. The Association has 16 bilingual member municipalities in Southern Finland”.</p> <p>Source: https://sydkusten.fi/sv/om/sydkusten/</p>
Archipelago Art Residency in Korpo	<p>“Our environment is a unique archipelago. With the National Parks and the Archipelago Sea Biosphere Reserve, frozen seas, light summer nights, rich birdlife as well as amazing star nights – this place has something to offer around the year”.</p> <p>Source: https://aark.fi/</p>
WWF Finland	<p>“Welcome to use WWF's Fish Guide! WWF's Fish Guide will help you make responsible fish choices. The guide guides you to responsible consumption at traffic lights. By following the guide's recommendations, you can contribute to ensuring that the world's oceans are not depleted”.</p> <p>Source: https://wwf.fi/ruoka/kalaopas/</p>
Suomen Latu (The Finnish Outdoor Association)	<p>“Suomen Latu is Finland's largest outdoor organisation”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.suomenlatu.fi/tietoa-meista.html</p>
Finnish Association for Nature Conservation (FANC)	<p>“The activities of the Finnish Association for Nature Conservation cover the entire country, from Hanko to the River Tenjoki. Nature is defended by about 150 local associations, which belong to 15 districts”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.sll.fi/</p>
City of Helsinki – Harakka Nature Centre	<p>“The Nature Center offers experiences, activities and information about the Baltic Sea, archipelago nature and a sustainable lifestyle”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.hel.fi/en/urban-environment-and-traffic/protection-of-the-environment-and-nature/environmental-education-and-the-nature-centre/harakka-nature-centre</p>
Archipelago Nature School (Luontokoulu)	<p>“We have more than 20 years of experience in the Nature School and our passion is to increase the interest in nature and provide positive experiences; Increase the respect for the environment and sustainability; Make the archipelago culture known and work for a living archipelago”.</p> <p>Source: https://luontokoulu.fi/en/</p>

Youth Environment Space, City of Helsinki	<p>“Young people’s power of initiative is a benefit provided by the City of Helsinki to its young residents to help young people be heard in the City’s decision-making”.</p> <p>Source: https://nuorten.hel.fi/en/take-part-and-make-a-difference/young-peoples-initiatives/</p>
Åbolands Ungdomsförbund (ÅUF) - Youth organisation in Åboland	<p>“ÅUF supports local youth associations and organises activities for children and young people. Turku Youth League ÅUF - ÅUF supports local youth associations and organises activities for children and young people”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.auf.fi/sv/start/</p>
Finnish Nature Association (Luontoliitto)	<p>“Every year, we organise more than 80 nature camps and excursions, as well as more than 300 school visits, and we support the activities of about 200 nature clubs”.</p> <p>Source: https://luontoliitto.fi/</p>
National Association of Finnish Islands (FÖSS)	<p>“An association for islanders and island life. Nearly 9,000 people in Finland live on islands that do not have a fixed road connection all year round. These are the primary beneficiaries of the bilingual NGO FÖSS”.</p> <p>Source: https://foss.fi/</p>
Åbolands naturskola rf/ Natur och miljö	<p>“The Turku Nature School is a regional centre of excellence for outdoor education in nature”.</p> <p>Source: https://biosfar.fi/partners/abolands-naturskola-rf-natur-och-miljo/</p>
Go Archipelago	<p>“Go Archipelago is a travel agency in the archipelago that wants to highlight small businesses and create a vibrant archipelago all year round. The company came about through a collaboration between four entrepreneurs active in the archipelago: chef and artist William Hellgren at Hotel Nestor, wilderness guide and tourism entrepreneur Sara Söderlund, multi-talented artist and designer Ida-Kajsa Johansson, and entrepreneur and bicycle rental artist Frank Tuominen”.</p> <p>Source: https://biosfar.fi/partners/go-archipelago-ab-oy/</p>
Ålands Natur & Miljö	<p>“Ålands Natur & Miljö is a politically independent popular movement with about 1000 members that works for the joy of nature, well-being and sustainability for the whole of Åland. The activities are diverse: everything from influencing decision-makers and authorities to organising excursions to scenic spots”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.natur.ax/</p>
<i>Beyond Finland</i>	
Baltic Region Heritage Committee	<p>“The Baltic Region Heritage Committee (BRHC) promotes the potential of cultural heritage as a strategic resource for developing the Baltic Sea Region”.</p> <p>Source: https://cbss.org/cbss-bodies/other-bodies/baltic-region-heritage-committee/</p>
Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission	<p>“The Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission – also known as the Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) – is an intergovernmental organisation (IGO) and a regional sea convention in the Baltic Sea area. A regional platform for environmental policy making, HELCOM was established in 1974 to protect the marine environment of the Baltic Sea from all sources of pollution”.</p> <p>Source: https://helcom.fi/about-us/</p>
Local institutions and municipalities	
University of Turku - Wave Riders – Center for Environmental Humanities	<p>“The University of Turku, established in 1920, has 8 faculties and 4 independent units. There are about 22,000 students and about 3,400 staff members”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.utu.fi/en/university/facts-and-figures “Wave Riders – Center for Environmental Humanities - Wave Riders (AHA–Aallonharjalle in Finnish) is an environmental research and education centre. Our background is in the humanities and social sciences”.</p> <p>Source: https://sites.utu.fi/aallonharjalle/en/</p>

Åbo Akademy - center of excellence Centre for Sustainable Ocean Science	“The Centre for Sustainable Ocean Science (SOS) provides transdisciplinary knowledge on wicked problems linked to marine biodiversity and its role in the societal transition to sustainability. SOS is an ÅAU Centre of Excellence funded by the Åbo Akademi University Foundation during 2024–2028”. Source: https://sites.abo.fi/centre-for-sustainable-ocean-science/about-us/
University of Helsinki - Social and cultural anthropology	“Social and cultural anthropology examines differences among human cultures and societies through comparative ethnographic analysis. The discipline of anthropology at the University of Helsinki is Finland’s largest unit in the field and provides researchers with strong connections to anthropological departments at universities abroad. At present, the discipline studies topics that include: the politics of border areas; state formation, climate change, and migration; the development of social cognition in culturally different contexts; and religious movements, secularism and the ethical and moral questions connected to them”. Source: https://www.helsinki.fi/en/faculty-social-sciences/research/disciplines-and-research-units/social-and-cultural-anthropology
Pictura – Konstila	Arts school for children, https://konstila.fi/fi/galleria/
Kimitoön Municipality	“Kimitoön is a scenic bilingual archipelago municipality in the province of Southwest Finland”. Source: https://www.kimitoon.fi/
Mariehamn – a City Built Around Maritime Heritage	“The sailing ship Pommern and the Maritime Museum, the Maritime Quarter with its boatbuilding tradition and the bustling ferry traffic to the east and west. In Mariehamn, the maritime heritage is obvious for a visitor—and has been for a long time”. Source: https://visitaland.com/en/experience/history/aland-history/a-town-built-around-shipping/
Projects and initiatives	
Cleaning of fish hiking trail, Holmviik	“In Holmviik, Hammarland, there are two previously frequent fish hiking trails that are currently clogged by reeds. Bovik and others’ fishing law and community intend to restore these for increased reproduction as part of the fishing conservation work in the fishing team”. Source: https://leader.ax/holmviik/
Culture & Pleasure in Vargata	“Wikens Wänner is a non-profit association in Vårdö with operations in Båthusviken. The association has over 100 members and manages a marina for locals and summer guests as well as a small guest harbor. Through this cultural project, the association wants to create an audio tour that preserves and highlights the history of “Katririna”, created by Sally Salminen’s bestseller from 1936. At the same time, two overgrown bathing bays are restored in the area to increase accessibility and well-being for visitors”. Source: https://leader.ax/kultur-trivsel-i-vargata/
Fishing beacons in the Åland archipelago	“The motivation of the fishing leader group: The project intends to preserve a cultural heritage while ensuring good conditions for fishing and navigation in the archipelago. The project promotes collaboration between several actors and has popular education elements”. Source: https://leader.ax/fiskefyrar-2/
Gudingens Inn	“During 2024-2027, Archipelago Pares r.f. (APrf) intends to carry out an innovative pilot trial at the eider colony around Stora and Lilla Båtskår in Lemland's southern archipelago. The experiment involves placing small blue mussel farms in the water in suitably protected places, as a complement to the extensive management measures already carried out on the islands”. Source: https://leader.ax/gudingens-gastgiveri/

Baltic herring and archipelago market	<p>“The project consists of two traditional herring and archipelago markets in Eckerö and Föglö in 2025 and 2026. The markets highlight our cultural heritage with Åland's food crafts and traditional handicrafts. The project is carried out by the Åland Hunting and Fishing Museum Foundation in collaboration with the Enterprising Archipelago and Åland Fishermen”. Source: https://leader.ax/strommings-och-skargardsmarknad/</p>
Thor's thanks	<p>“The Fibula Ancient Association has decided to build a new roof at Långhuset in the Viking Village for catering and events. The aim is to further develop the business throughout the year and not just the summer season”. Source: https://leader.ax/tors-tak/</p>
The sea is our way	<p>“Åland Nature School plans and implements the teaching theme "The sea is our way 2025-2027" in the Maritime Quarter in Mariehamn for school children in grades 4-5. The goal is to give the students the opportunity to experience and learn about fishing, archipelago life and archipelago culture linked to peasant sailing in an authentic environment. The theme is interdisciplinary and the students get to take part in our cultural heritage through practical boat handling, fishing/fish handling and crafts. The students get to smell the tar and wood and try flavors from the past in the form of salted herring and sour bread. The theme days are carried out in collaboration with other organisations in the Maritime Quarter. The goal is to reach about 800 students in three years”. Source: https://leader.ax/havet-ar-var-vag/</p>
Skiftet's Pensioners' Parliament in Åland	<p>“Mariehamn Pensioners' Association and Northern Åland Pensioners work together with the pensioners' associations in Åboland to create long-term cooperation and strengthen pensioners' well-being, health and participation in society. The Skiftets Pensionersparlament project will hold three parliaments during the period 2025–2027 – one in Åland and two in the Turku archipelago”. Source: https://leader.ax/skiftets-pensionarsparlament-pa-aland/</p>
Bockholm's beach	<p>“Skeppargården Pellas ry owns a 5.1 ha area Lemland Granboda, which today is partly a clear-cut area (approx. 1 ha). The area is adjacent to Lumparn with beautiful surrounding nature. The project will create a natural meadow and bathing area for locals and visitors. As more and more of the village's beach areas are exploited, it becomes difficult for non-beach owners to find suitable bathing spots. The association also runs an active tourism industry and visitors often ask for a beach where they can swim or engage in outdoor activities”. Source: https://leader.ax/bockholms-strand/</p>
HIKING TRAIL LÅNGA UDDEN	<p>“Asterholmas Byalag wants to develop the attractiveness of the island of Asterholma in Brändö municipality by making the unique archipelago nature that Långa Udden offers available to visitors and residents, by establishing a hiking trail”. Source: https://leader.ax/vandringsled-langa-udden/</p>
Friday meetings for seniors	<p>“Of Kumlinge municipality's almost 300 inhabitants, just over a third are pensioners. The main purpose of the project is to engage, inform and interest older people with different kinds of programs and shared meals to counteract loneliness and increase the social contact surfaces of the elderly. Part of the project's content aims to broaden the knowledge and skills of the elderly in everyday life, while part of the content will function mainly as a tool for social interaction. In other words, both benefit and pleasure for increased quality of life”. Source: https://leader.ax/fredagstraffar-for-seniorer/</p>
Renovation of a fishing cabin on Dömmarskär	<p>“Enklinge fishing team manages a fishing cabin on the islet of Dömmarskär, west of Enklinge. Holmen is part of Enklinge's common land areas and there has previously been a fishing village. The cottage is in great need of renovation to be used by future generations. The idea is that a large part of the work will be carried out on a voluntary basis. The target group is local locals, local</p>

	fishermen and anglers”. Source: https://leader.ax/renovering-av-fiskestuga-pa-dommarskar/
Såvera Södersundet!	“The Finnö, Österbygge, and Öfverboda fishing teams intend to join forces to restore an important biotope for fish and birds and thus create conditions for further work for environmental protection”. Source: https://leader.ax/savera-sodersundet/
Fishing lighthouses	“Åland Fishermen and Åland Sea Rescue Society, in cooperation with the Åland Provincial Government, are restoring and restoring nine fishing lighthouses in the Åland archipelago; Bolmklubben, Hundklubben, Kalven, Långören, Rannö, Salklobb, Stångskär, Ytterlångskärskobb and Ådskär. All work is done with volunteer work, volunteers”. Source: https://leader.ax/fiskefyrar/
Make use of seal skins	“Ålands Slöjd och konsthantverk organises courses in organic, traditional tanning and sewing of sealskin. In order to increase interest in ethical seal hunting and thus be able to protect local fish stocks more effectively, we need to have the knowledge to take advantage of the prey”. Source: https://leader.ax/ta-tillvara-salskinn/
The Fisheries Local Action Group – FLAG, or Fisheries Leader Group	The Fisheries Local Action Group – FLAG, or Fisheries Leader Group, https://leader.ax/fiskeleader/
<i>Beyond Finland</i>	
Young People Network for Balticness	“Youth and future generation involvement becomes a more and more prominent issue for the Baltic Sea Region politics, development and identity. In response to this challenge the Young People Network for Balticness (YoPeNET) aims at establishing long-term cooperation among partners in the Baltic Sea region, with the purpose of educating and supporting the voice of young people in the critical dialogue concerning history, cultural heritage, regional identity and the future of the Baltic Sea Region”. Source: https://yopenet.ug.edu.pl/

Ráckeve, Hungary

Table 3. List of communities mapped in the region of Ráckeve, Hungary.

Title	Description
Local NGOs, Charities & Foundations environment and art related	
Ráckeve Danube Branch Angling Association - Ráckevei Dunaági Horgász Szövetség	“We would like the water of the Danube branch to be clean, bath-able all the way through, and to regain its old reputation. We would like the younger generation to join our fishing camp in increasing numbers, if our children would become environmentalists and nature-loving people. We would like our branch of the Danube to remain a peaceful, quiet recreation area that preserves its natural beauty and values, providing a lot of joy to its admirers”. Source: https://www.rdhsz.hu/index.php/rolunk/a-szovetseg-tortenete-eredmenyei
Ráckeve Artist Association (Ráckevei Alkotói Kör)	Ráckevei Alkotói Kör, Source: https://www.facebook.com/groups/281202458972359/
Ráckevei Molnár Céh Alapítvány (Shipmiller’s Guild of Ráckeve, Foundation)	“In December 2007, the Ráckevei Molnár Céh Foundation was established. During the construction of the mill, help came from residents of other towns and from those living abroad who wanted to assist. Everyone contributed to the mill with what they could: some with their labor, some with donations, some with old mill artifacts, and some with their expertise. The Ráckevei Watermill is proof of the community's cohesive strength”. Source: https://www.facebook.com/groups/335751166442561/?locale=hu_HU
Őszidő Nyugdíjas Klub (Autumn-time Pensionates Club)	“The Autumn Time Pensioners' Club has been operating in Ráckeve for 20 years, with nearly 70 members. It not only brings together the city's retirees but also strives to enrich their leisure time with interesting programs and excursions”. Source: http://akmk.hu/oszido-nyugdijas-klub/
Danube Friends Association of Ráckeve	Balabán cruise ship. Source: https://www.rackevetersege.hu/index_php/szolgáltatások/szolgáltatásaink-rackeven/139-balaban-setahajo/
Szigetcsücske Természetjáró Egyesület (Island-end Nature-treacking Association)	Sziget-csücske Nature Friends Association, Source: http://szigetcsucske.hupont.hu/5/fo-oldal
Keve Serege Ijász Egyesület	“Keve Serege Archery Association is an active organisation, gives shows and take apart in traditional programs in Ráckeve”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/191
Ráckevei Horgász Egyesület	“Fishing Association in the small Danube branch”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/200
Magyarországi Harmonikasok Kulturális Egyesülete	“They primarily want to help the survival of quality music culture and quality live music. Using the definition of quality live music, it is considered important that chamber music productions of artists active in the fields of folk music, world music, musical literature, jazz and classical music gain space, showing the joy of playing together. They want to help dedicated musicians of the aforementioned genres. They want to pay special attention to young talents starting their careers, minority or other disadvantaged Hungarian musicians, and Hungarian musicians from across the border”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/209
Ráckeve4 Leisure Sport Association (Ráckeve4 Szabadidősport Egyesület)	“The Association was founded by active runners, and it organises many running events as well as a national marathon race in this area”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/216
Miller Guild Foundation of Ráckeve	“Besides the different collective activities, the goals of the Miller Guild Foundation is the exploration of objects and historical memories regarding the ship mill of Ráckeve, rebuilding and making the old ship mill work, as well as the exploration and safekeeping of the cultural heritage”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/188

Rackeve Ertek Egyesulet	“The aim of the association is to preserve the cultural values of Ráckeve and its region, to nurture the traditions, to organize various cultural programs and to produce publications”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/196
Keve Galeria	“Various contemporary art and applied art exhibitions throughout the year”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/190
Ács Károly Művelődési Központ	“The Center of Culture Ács Károly is one of the most important organizers of cultural life in Ráckeve. They organise beside the biggest traditional programs, diverse cultural programs for all age-groups and for many interests. There are many exhibitions, concerts, conferences, performances. They try to create programs to support activities like dancing, arts and crafts, and give help to many other local organisations”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/821
Magyar Halászati Kultúráért Alapítvány	“Foundation for the Culture of the Hungarian Fishery wants to preserve and show its large collection of heritage about fishing and fishery”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/831
Szitakoto Dragonfly Association (NGO)	“The Association aims to bring into being some joint initiatives and „good causes”, as well as to organise cultural and artistic programs involving the whole society. The Association also initiated the so-called „KÖZÖSS(t)ÉG” project”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/217
Aqualand Termalfurdo es elmenyfurdo	“The Aqua Land complex in Ráckeve offers its guests the healing experiences of thermal water and healing water, both outdoors and indoors, on an area of nearly 5 hectares. With the permanent operation of some of our departments, and the periodic operation of other departments, we provide complex, healing wellness experiences suitable for the season”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/181

Local institutions and municipalities

Municipality of Ráckeve	Municipality of Ráckeve, Source: https://www.rackeve.hu/onkormanyzat/intezmenyek/
Arpad Fejedelem Altalanos Iskola	Arpad Fejedelem Elementary School, Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/183
Rackeve Szent Imre Katolikus Altalanos Iskola	“In Ráckeve, in a wonderful natural environment, on the banks of the Little Danube, the Catholic school, built with the cooperation of parishes, was consecrated in 1897, whose patron saint was Prince Saint Imre. The institution operated as an independent institution until nationalization. In 2001, the school adopted the name Szent Imre”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/197
Muveszetoktatasi Intezmeny	“György Ránki Elementary School of Art began its operation in 1983 as a Regional State Music School with five outsourced classes. They gradually became independent by the end of the 80s. In addition to the city of Ráckeve, we currently perform the tasks of elementary art education in Szigetszentmárton. The 1999/2000 was transformed into an art school in the academic year. In addition to classical music - in accordance with the needs of the city - it teaches various branches of dance and visual arts. It took the name of composer György Ránki on the school's 20th anniversary”. Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/205
Skarica Mate Varosi Konyvtar	Library in Ráckeve, Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/206
Patay Laszlo Varosi Keptar	“At the foot of the Árpád bridge is the city gallery belonging to the museum, which was opened in 1997 by the city of Ráckeve at the initiative of László Patay, Munkácsy prize-winning painter. On the lower floor, the famous 19th-20th century paintings borrowed from the Hungarian National Gallery and other national museums. Visitors can view paintings by representatives of naturalistic Hungarian painting

	<p>schools and workshops of the 19th century. On the upper level of the gallery, the extraordinary exhibition of László Patay, who died in 2002, can be viewed. One of the most interesting works is the vision of the master, who was nearing the end of his life, about the synthesis of fine art”.</p> <p>Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/193</p>
<p>Projects and initiatives</p>	
<p>Student government Association of the Ady Andre Gymnasium</p>	<p>Participation in Danube environmental activities,</p> <p>Source : https://www.radyg.hu/index.php/neveles/dok</p>
<p>Serfőző Tamás</p>	<p>“He is the owner and chef of the 'Vidék Íze' - Taste of the Countryside which is a Home Restaurant on the riverside”.</p> <p>Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/810</p>
<p>Bodzan Antal</p>	<p>“Bodzan Antal is an architect and sculptor. He has been making statues since 1997”.</p> <p>Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/organization/stakeholder/867</p>
<p>Development of Angyali-sziget</p>	<p>“On the small Danube island where there are mostly holiday homes, owners initially cooperated to solve the garbage problems and carried out garbage collection campaigns. After resolving the acute problem, the community of inhabitants set other goals for themselves and established a non-governmental organization. Their long-term goals include solving sewerage, tackling the garbage and the parking issue, creating community space and community piers. They organize concerts, community-building workshops, brainstorming events. They build a social network for helping each other, and they have been collecting different skills of the inhabitants, for example by creating the local "Golden Pages"”.</p> <p>Source: https://platform.danurb.eu/#/projects/project/90</p>
<p>Beyond Reckeve</p>	
<p>DANUBE4all</p>	<p>“Thus, DANUBE4all seeks to integrate action on these environmental concerns with social and economic wellbeing; embracing a science-to-people approach that actively integrates public interests and empowers all Danube stakeholders”. Source: https://www.danube4allproject.eu/about</p>

Venice, Italy

Table 4. List of communities mapped in the region of Veneto, Italy.

Title	Description
Local NGOs, Charities & Foundations environment and art related	
We are here Venice	<p>“We are here Venice is a Third Sector Organisation (TSO), registered in the Joint National Register of the Third Sector, dedicated to the conservation of Venice as a living city. Founded in 2015, it operates both as a research collective and activist platform, reinforcing connections between the best available sources of information, stakeholders, and the local community. Venice, with its specificity, its history and its cultural intricacies, represents a unique context for exploring and acting on innovative policies of resilience. Our initiatives range from specific projects, such as research and fieldwork, to broad awareness-raising campaigns”. Source: https://www.weareherevenice.org/introduction/</p>
The Tidal Garden	<p>“The Tidal Garden is a Venice-based research agency that explores the edible potential of halophytes - salt-tolerant plants - as a tool for cultural adaptation to climate change. Led by Filippo Grassi (environmental scientist), Lodovica Guarnieri (designer/researcher) and Lorenzo Barbasetti di Prun (chef/artist), in collaboration with a network of farmers and gastronomic professionals, the project focuses on establishing the cultivation of new crops and developing novel culinary habits from salinised agricultural fields”. Source: https://thetidalgarden.earth/The-Project-1 More about the work of Lorenzo Barbasetti di Prun in the film Elementi Minimi, https://www.earthfuturesfestival.com/the-films/v/elementi-minimi</p>
Venice Lagoon Plastic Free	<p>“Venice Lagoon Plastic Free (VLPF) is a non-profit organization listed on the National Single Third Sector Registry (RUNTS) and based in the historic city centre of Venice. VLPF uses the World Heritage site of Venice and its lagoon as a laboratory for developing and testing innovative solutions for marine litter pollution prevention, monitoring, management, remediation and sustainable blue circular economy initiatives that can be shared and transferred at regional, national, European, and international levels”. Source: https://www.plasticfreevenice.org/about-us</p>
European Cultural Centre	<p>“The ECC-Italy in Venice mainly organises contemporary art, architecture and design exhibitions. In addition, we organise symposiums, meetings, workshops, educational programs and many other cultural events. We wish to make it possible for all people to visit our events always free of charge. Our events in Venice are visited by over 600.000 people every year. Since we want to stay as independent and transparent as possible, we choose to finance our activities with the support of those organisations and people who participate in our projects, without the waste of taxpayers' money”. Source: https://ecc-italy.eu/about/aboutus</p>
TOCIA! cucina e comunità	<p>“[A] collective that employs convivial research around food as a tool to investigate the human and non-human landscape of the lagoon. Named after the Venetian "tociare"—the act of taking a piece of bread, polenta or even your fingers and dipping it into a sauce, Toccia! brings together cooks, farmers, gatherers, fishermen, activists, researchers, artists, and craftsmen. The project enhances the territory and the communities that make it by developing research on products, recovery and preservation techniques, and culinary contaminations”. Source: https://tba21.org/sapidsoilprelude</p>
UNESCO Office in Venice UNESCO Regional Bureau for Science and Culture in Europe, Venice (Italy)	<p>“The Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC/UNESCO) promotes international cooperation in marine sciences to improve management of the ocean, coasts and marine resources”. Source: https://www.ioc.unesco.org/en</p>

Venetian Society of Natural Sciences Società Veneziana di Scienze Naturali	<p>“The Venetian Society of Natural Sciences was established in Venice in December 1975 as a non-profit cultural-scientific association. Its birth responded to the need, increasingly felt by Venetian naturalists, for collaboration, participation and sharing in research and dissemination activities in the Natural Sciences. Paolo Cesari was its soul and inspirer”. Source: https://www.svsn.it/storia/</p>
Natural History Museum, Venice	<p>“The Natural History Museum of Venice Giancarlo Ligabue: promotes scientific researches, organises educational activities for schools, opens to the public a rich naturalistic library, guarantee conservation, restauration, cataloguing and increasing of its naturalistic collections, offer educational services in the scientific-naturalistic field, through permanent and temporary exhibitions, courses and conferences, laboratories and editorial activities”. Source: https://msn.visitmuve.it/en/the-museum/about-us/</p>
Museum – M9	<p>“M9 belongs to a new generation of museums. For the very first time, a museum narrates the compelling history of the 20th century”. Source: https://www.m9museum.it/</p>
Fishing Cooperative: The Cooperativa San Marco - Fishermen of Burano	<p>“The Cooperativa San Marco - Fishermen of Burano is composed of about 90 associates. The cooperative deals with shellfish farming and small coastal fishing, offering members services of refrigeration, labelling, ice and fish packaging. It manages two sales parking spaces at the Fish Market at the Wholesale of Venice. To diversify the offer and combine local fishing with tourism, the cooperative has developed, in collaboration with Regione Veneto, the activity of pesca tourism”. Source: https://www.cooperativasanmarco.com/</p>
Association of fishermen Carmagnolesi	<p>“The Fishermen's Association was founded in 1971 and since that date has always dealt with the Municipal Fishing Reserve of Carmagnola. It establishes the rules, exercises control over fishing and restocking”. Source: http://www.riservacarmagnola.it/</p>
CIV - Consorzio Ittico Veneziano	<p>“New consortium of fisheries management in the northern basin of the Venice lagoon”. Source: https://consorzioitticoveneziano.it/</p>
The Center of the Lagoon Civilization	<p>“The center of the lagoon civilization has on display many objects of the typical Venetian culture. A journey to discover a millenary culture that we want to preserve for future generations”. Source: https://www.centrociviltalagunare.it/</p>
Società Cooperativa Sestante di Venezia	<p>“We are a group of educators, trainers, psychologists and naturalistic guides who since 2000 invests skills and professionalism, with the aim of contributing to the development of our territory through training, education, animation and sustainable tourism”. Source: https://sestantedivenezia.it/it</p>
Marevivo Veneto	<p>“We are an environmental protection organization against pollution and illegal fishing and in defense of biodiversity. From rivers to lakes, from the Po Delta to the Venice Lagoon, we are committed to protecting and cleaning up the waters, coasts and beaches of Veneto”. Source: https://marevivoveneto.it/</p>
SEA BEYOND Ocean Literacy Centre	<p>“the SEA BEYOND Ocean Literacy Centre, a dynamic space in the Venetian Lagoon co-designed by the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (UNESCO-IOC) and CRA - Carlo Ratti Associati. Inaugurated in 2025 by the Prada Group and UNESCO-IOC, the centre is dedicated to fostering knowledge and understanding of the ocean, raising awareness of its fundamental role for life on Earth”. Source: https://oceanliteracycentre.org/</p>
<i>Beyond Veneto region</i>	
SDSN Youth Mediterranean	<p>“Mediterranean Youth Network SDSN Youth Mediterranean is hosted by the Santa Chiara Lab Research & Innovation Centre of the University of Siena (Siena, Italy)”. Source: https://www.sdsnyouth.org/networks/mediterranean</p>

Local institutions and municipalities

Ca'Foscari university of Venice	<p>"(...) a public university, founded on 6 August 1868 as Scuola Superiore di Commercio. We have reached a high national and international standing with the quality of our research and teaching, which reaches across countries and disciplines".</p> <p>Source: https://www.unive.it/pag/17956/</p>
Venice International University	<p>"VIU, together with its constituents, seeks to contribute to the creation of knowledge, understanding, and skills, and to respond to current and future major societal challenges faced by humankind today: environmental, social, cultural and technological phenomena and their local impacts. Knowledge creation across the disciplines - the humanities, social sciences, and the sciences - can play a fundamental role in coping with the Global Challenges".</p> <p>Source: https://univiu.org/about-viu/what-is-viu</p>
Global Campus of Human Rights	<p>"With eight regional programmes delivered by over 100 prestigious universities, the Global Campus is the world's largest network for postgraduate education in human rights and democratisation. The vision of the Global Campus of Human Rights is to foster new generations of human rights experts able to contribute to a world in which human dignity, equality, freedom, human security, sustainable development, democracy, the rule of law and respect for all human rights are realised".</p> <p>Source: https://www.gchumanrights.org/who-we-are/</p>
The Institute of Marine Sciences (CNR-ISMAR)	<p>"Our mission is to advance fundamental and applied research in the fields of physical, chemical, and biological oceanography, as well as marine geology. We are dedicated to enhancing our understanding of ocean processes and climate variability while developing innovative systems and services for the observation, protection, and sustainable management of marine environments and coastal areas. Our headquarters is situated in the historic city of Venice, complemented by six branch offices across Italy, located in Bologna, Lerici (SP), Naples, Palermo, Rome, and Trieste. We also operate in Milan and Florence, further expanding our reach and collaboration opportunities".</p> <p>Source: https://www.ismar.cnr.it/web-content/en/about-us/</p>
Beyond Veneto region	
Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale (ISPRA)	<p>Main fields of research: "taxonomy of benthic species in marine (incl. phytobenthos) and lagoon systems, biology and physiology of commercial species, chemical oceanography and monitoring of contaminants in the water column, sediments and biota in both natural and anthropic environments (ports, offshore platforms, industrial coastal zones), biomagnification".</p> <p>Source: https://www.ciesm.org/online/institutes/institute.php?instID=IT7</p>
Laboratorio di Biologia Marina e Pesca University of Bologna	<p>Main fields of research: "fishery research, fish biology".</p> <p>Source: https://www.ciesm.org/online/institutes/institute.php?instID=IT8</p>
Istituto per le Risorse Biologiche e le Biotecnologie Marine (Ancona) CNR-IRBIM	<p>Main fields of research: "biology and ecology of marine organisms, included alien species; spatial distribution, population dynamics, stock assessment of fisheries resources; marine microbial ecology and biotechnology, bio-prospecting; technology development for sustainable fisheries; monitoring platforms for marine ecosystems; integrated Coastal Zone Management (IZCM) for a sustainable development of marine resources and Biodiversity conservation".</p> <p>Source: https://www.ciesm.org/online/institutes/institute.php?instID=IT1</p>
Projects and initiatives	
MICRO Citizen Science for Innovative Micro-Plastic Assessment in Venice	<p>"MICRO is coordinated by Venice Lagoon Plastic Free with support from IMG Group, a prominent Portuguese industrial group in the polymer sector, and the participation of teachers and students from the Chemistry Department of the "G. e M. Montani" Technical Technological Institute city of Fermo".</p> <p>Sources: https://www.plasticfreevenice.org/citizen-science-for-innovative-micro-plastic-assessment-in-venice</p>
Maker Mile	<p>"Maker Mile is a project born in Venice to focus attention on the artisans who</p>

	<p>contribute to defining the identity of the lagoon". Source: https://www.linkedin.com/company/makermile/about/</p>
Squero San Trovaso	<p>"Squero: Typical construction site where they are created, build and repair the boats of small dimensions such as gondolas, puppets, Sandoli, Sciopòni and other boats typical of the Venetian lagoon tradition". Source: http://www.squerosantrovaso.com/</p>
Rethinking the Water Museum of Venice	<p>"The idea is to enlarge the pilot project of this network to create an interregional ecomuseum". Source: https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/node/254379</p>
Venetian Rowing courses	<p>"Venetian Rowing is an ancient Venetian rowing technique in which rowers stand as they row forward. This technique is suited to different types of boat, among which the Carolina – a Venetian boat with a flat bottom and a bow and stern that are elongated upwards and exactly equal, and which is best suited for beginners". Source: https://www.unive.it/pag/42468/</p>
The International Center for the Humanities and Social Change	<p>"NICHE aims to produce transdisciplinary environmental scholarship and public engagement initiatives where environmental humanities can play a major role. The focus of NICHE will lie on five interconnected programs and research areas that intersect with those of THE NEW INSTITUTE and its stated aim to find viable pathways to solutions for our common future. ". Source: https://www.unive.it/pag/44234/</p>
Biocultural Diversity Lab	<p>"The focal points of the laboratory's permanent activities are the evolution of knowledge and practices related to the relationships between humans and the environment, both today and in past centuries, through the use of various qualitative and quantitative methods employed in various disciplines. The main fields of research application are education, the development of local products, participatory conservation strategies, and policy suggestions". Source: https://unive.it/pag/45985/</p>
VIU participates as "Residency Host" in the S+T+ARTS4waterII Residency Program	<p>"S+T+ARTS4waterII Residency Program is dedicated to Water Sustainability and innovation at the nexus of Science, Technology, and the arts. This II edition specifically focuses on the environmental challenges of ports, port cities, coastal areas, and waterways". Source: https://www.univiu.org/viu-life/news-archive/2561-starts4waterii-residencies-for-artists</p>
WaterLANDS: Water-based solutions for carbon storage, people and wilderness	<p>"WaterLANDS is a €23.6 million, 5-year EU-funded project that will restore wetland sites across Europe and lay the foundations for scalable protection across much wider areas". Source: https://waterlands.eu/</p>
The Lazzaretti Veneziani project	<p>"The Lazzaretti Veneziani project is promoted by two associations: Ekos Club and the Venice Chapter of the Archeoclub d'Italia. The project headquarters are on the island of Lazzaretto Nuovo, in the northern part of the Venice Laguna, the only one of the lesser islands of the Venetian archipelago to have been rescued from neglect and returned to the enjoyment of the general public thanks to a no-profit initiative. Today, the island is an ecomuseum dedicated to the local territory and its communities: projects and management are driven by the dedication and knowledge of hundreds of enthusiasts and volunteers, in collaboration with institutions and dozens of local, national and international organizations". Source: https://lazzarettiveneziani.it/en/home/project</p>
ONA Short Film Festival	<p>"ONA Short Film Festival aims to share life-changing stories of outdoor sports, nature, and environmental awareness. We believe these themes can have a vital impact on today's society. Direct contact with nature awakens us to the knowledge that we are a pivotal piece of the environment in which we live, and have a responsibility to protect it. Outdoor sports ultimately teach us values that create more sensitive people, and a better world for many more adventurers to come". Source: https://onafilmfestival.com/the-festival/</p>

Rialto Fish market Venice	<p>“For about a thousand years the island of Rialto constituted the commercial heart of the city of Venice and for centuries was also the true centre of a «world economy» – as the French historian Fernand Braudel defined it in 1949, referring in particular to the period between the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries”.</p> <p>Source: https://padovauniversitypress.it/system/files/attachments/2023-09/9788869383038_0.pdf#page=12</p>
Spazio Punch	<p>“Founded in 2011, is a non-profit Venetian organization on the Giudecca island that investigates and organizes cultural events, exhibitions and talks”. Source: https://www.spaziopunch.com/about</p>
CLEAN LAGOON PROJECT	<p>“The purpose of the "Clean Lagoon Project" is therefore to contribute to making the Venice lagoon cleaner, in particular the Chioggia area, by collecting abandoned plastic, but also by raising awareness of the emergency caused by the abandonment of waste, promoting a new respectful behavior towards the lagoon environment”. Source: https://www.lagunapulita.it/mission.html</p>
Legambiente Veneto	<p>“The itinerant citizen science and scientific environmentalism campaign "Operation Rivers – Exploring to Preserve", created by Legambiente Veneto in collaboration with ARPAV, under the patronage of the Eastern Alps District Basin Authority”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.legambienteveneto.it/</p>
Lab 1: Venice – “Citizen Science for Marine Conservation”	<p>“At the end of the lab, during the co-creation phase, participants were divided in five groups, each working on designing and prototyping a project upon the four keywords mentioned above. In the following text, you can read the abstracts from each of these projects”.</p> <p>Source: https://www.steamtalent.eu/lab-1-venice-citizen-science-for-marine-conservation/</p>
<i>Beyond Veneto region</i>	
MEDiverSEAty Consortium	<p>“MEDiverSEAty Consortium covers a broad and representative spectrum of the European countries actively involved in the management of marine resources in the Mediterranean”.</p> <p>Source: https://mediverseaty.eu/</p>

Acknowledgment

Acknowledgment

Inputs from Mission Ocean community and beyond have brought support for this report in order to reach a comprehensive overview of organizations and individuals being present at the four residency sites. We are grateful to Andreia Gonçalves Sousa, Morgan Rhys Dennis Mano Casal Ribeiro as well as Blue Mission AA team, particularly colleagues from Azores Archipelago – Diana Sousa, Tania Li Chen, Taynara S. Louzada as well as Shift Cost Action members: Kiat Ng and Julia Bentz. Many thanks also to Fabio Carella for support regarding Venice Lagoon communities. For input regarding Hungary many thanks to Alexandra Czeglédi and Bálint Balázs, as well as Baranya Sándor and members from the DANUrB Interreg project and FOSTER project. For the Baltic Sea input many thanks to Kirsi Sonck-Rautio, Tsipe Aavik and Monika Suškevičs. Also great thanks to TIDAL ArtS team and MaREI UCC colleague - Catriona Iulia Reid and Kathrin Kopke. Many thanks also to those joining mini podcast series and follow up zoom sessions for further inputs, special thanks to Chiara Spadaro and Erica Villa as well as Katja Bonnevier, Tuuli Toivola, Attila Toth and Gábor Beliczay.

TIDAL ARTS

Transforming and Inspiring
Aquatic Landscapes Through
Art and Sciences

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement ID 101157796. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.